

EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBE CONTENTS ON FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF THERMALLY DEGRADED NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS VIA THE ESSENTIAL WORK OF FRACTURE TEST

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Introduction

Fig. Trend of global electric vehicle sales **Fig.** Battery pack positioned below (Tesla S) **Fig.** Underbody protection (Tesla S) **Fig.** A process from raw material to product

<Backgrounds>

- Power of electric vehicle is electric battery.
- A battery pack is located below the vehicle and is protected by underbody shield.
- It should be strong enough to protect a battery pack from some sort of obstruction and also be light enough for better fuel efficiency.

<Objectives>

- Final goal is to make a product to protect a battery pack.
- For lightweighting, we used carbon fiber reinforced plastics with nanofillers.
- This study is to construct baseline data of raw materials.

Materials and Test Methods

Matrix	Nanofiller
Polyethylene Terephthalate with Glycol (PETG)	Multi-walled carbon nanotube (CNT)
SK Chem. (PN100)	Nanocyl (NC7000)

Fig. Materials information

Ø48, twin crew extruder

PETG/CNT nanocomposite films	
CNT contents	0, 0.5, 1, 2wt%
Thickness	50 µm

Fig. PETG/CNT nanocomposite pellets

Ø25, L/D ratio 30:1, single crew extruder

Barrel temp.	Screw speed	Die temp.
230°C	20 rpm	225°C
Cooling roll temp.		Cooling roll speed
80°C (Top&Middle) 30°C (Bottom)		3.5 m/min

Fig. PETG/CNT nanocomposite films

Test Methods	Property	Value
Thermal Degradation	Temperature	60 °C
	Time	0, 100, 200, 400 hrs
Fracture test (EWF test)	Strain rate	50 mm/min
	Notch direction	Transverse Direction

Fig. Test conditions

Results and Discussion

Fig. (a) ATR-FTIR (b) Carboxyl Index curve – of PETG films **Fig.** EWF parameters

Fig. 'Ligament vs. Specific work of fracture' linear regression lines of (a) 0h (b) 100h (c) 200h (d) 400h

Fig. SEM images of fracture surfaces PETG/CNT films (a) CNT 0wt% (b) CNT 0.5wt% (c) CNT 1wt% (d) CNT 2wt%

Conclusion

- PETG/CNT nanocomposite films with various kinds of CNT contents were studied.
- They were thermally degraded by heat and qualified by ATR-FTIR and their fracture properties were studied by EWF test method.
- It is natural that CNTs make films weaker to crack propagation.
- We expected that CNTs make nanocomposite films have stronger resistance to crack initiation. (fracture toughness)

<Future work>

- We need to figure out why nanocomposite films have poorer fracture properties and find the solution.
- We will produce carbon fiber reinforced nanocomposite sheets and need to check their mechanical, fractural and other kinds of properties.